

**D6.9 Report on the Second One
Health EJP Continuing
Professional Development
Module (Y3)**

WP6: Education and Training

Responsible Partner: UoS (P23)

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	Report no 2 on OHEJP Continuing Professional Development module
WP and task	WP6, Task 6.5: One Health Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Module
Lead Organising Institute	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)
Lead Event Organiser	Matthias Filter
Local Organising Committee	Matthias Filter, Marion Gottschald, Alexander Falenski, Yvonne Mensching, Jakub Fusiak
Collaborating Organising Institutes	University of Surrey (UoS) Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark (DTU Food) French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES)

	Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI) Robert Koch Institute (RKI) Pensoft Publishers
Collaborating Organisers	Professor Roberto La Ragione, Dr Piyali Basu, Dr Jade Passey, Elaine Campling, Dr Dan Horton, Fernanda Dórea
Due month of the deliverable	40
Actual submission month	40
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EMA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO-EU <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s): </p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s): ORION, COHESIVE, RADAR, subscribers to OHEJP Education and Training monthly bulletin.....</p>

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Introduction

The German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) organised and hosted the One Health EJP's Second CPD Module which focused on Digital Innovation for One Health Practitioners. They presented software tools to support researchers and One Health professionals in various data collection and analysis tasks including those linked with outbreak investigations and the trace back of food products. These solutions have the potential to support the whole One Health community including national and international risk assessment agencies, risk managers and academic institutions.

The CPD Module was specifically designed to share knowledge on relevant software tools and train their practical adoption. In an increasingly digital world, innovative training opportunities like e-learning courses and online course will become increasingly important.

Organisation of the (virtual) workshop

Initially this workshop was proposed to be a physical event. However, due to COVID-19, the WP6 team advised early by September 2020 to re-plan this event as a virtual event as it was very unlikely that travel restrictions would have been lifted in February 2021. The advantages of a virtual event included low overhead costs and potentially more delegates to attend at lower costs.

Thus, the event programme was re-structured to meet the needs of a virtual event, consisting of a mixture of online lectures and interactive breakout sessions, live demos and exercises, all combined with the e-learning courses.

After testing web-conferencing systems to ensure a smooth and stable running for at least estimated 100 to 150 participants, it was decided to use Zoom to host the workshop. Also, good experiences from past events regarding the tool promised to ensure a smooth running of the event.

In addition, it was planned to create online courses in a dedicated [e-learning platform](#). Therefore, the BfR-Team compared several e-learning platforms and finally opted for the open-source platform Moodle. A contract with a German certified Moodle distributor to host and provide the service was closed.

Theme and Overview

The one-week CPD module centred around the use of innovative open-source software solutions supporting risk assessment, zoonotic outbreak investigations and data interoperability. The objective of this training module was to introduce new tools and technologies for One Health researchers and professionals. Specifically, solutions that support foodborne-disease outbreak investigations, efficient surveillance data integration as well as the re-use of risk assessment models were introduced. The solutions presented

have the potential to support the whole One Health community including national and international risk assessment agencies, risk managers and academic institutions.

Aims and Objectives

Dealing with different software tools is extraordinarily important within the One Health community. The knowledge about and training on how to use available open source software solutions is essential and a continuously ongoing effort. In order to achieve a broad use of the tools by the scientific community, One Health practitioners and stakeholders, it is crucial however to provide support and training which was one goal to aim at.

The event therefore encouraged knowledge sharing and allowed participants to present their own digital innovation tools. Besides that, the workshops linked the efforts and outcomes of several One Health EJP Joint Research and Integrative projects (ORION, COHESIVE, RADAR). For example, in the framework of COHESIVE, the integrative supply chain tracing platform FoodChain-Lab Web was presented.

At the end of the CPD module, participants had the opportunity to provide feedback to the software developer teams and to bring up new feature requests or development goals.

As the e-learning course as well as the workshop material remains available online until November 2021, the workshop could easily be replicated in the future by others. This also contributes to the sustainability of the software tools after the end of funding of the different OHEJP projects involved.

For the tutors (that are partly directly involved in the software development process) the feedback received during the hands-on sessions was of high importance to their further work.

Experts and Speakers

The virtual training was delivered by senior research scientists from BfR and partners from the OHEJP consortium, including SVA, DTU Food, ANSES, RKI and NVI and OHEJP stakeholders, EFSA with an extensive track record in providing training for research scientists from different research domains (specifically food science, but also for researchers in public health and animal health). More information and biographies are available on the [OHEJP Website](#).

Programme Structure

The CPD 2021 module was organised as a one-week training event that was paralleled by new e-learning courses. The workshop week started on Monday 15th February 2021 with a set of plenary lectures on innovative digital tools. Experts from BfR, ANSES, DTU Food, RKI and EFSA presented on this day. These lectures provided an introduction into relevant application scenarios of innovative digital solutions from the domain of food safety, public health and animal health. On this day the organisers issued a call for participation for a digital innovations forum to all participants which was included in the programme of the last day of the event (19th February 2021).

On Tuesday, Wednesday and Thursday, 16th to 18th February 2021, participants attended interactive hands-on trainings on the following software tools:

[FoodChain-Lab](#) (BfR), 16th February

[Data interoperability in One Health](#): data FAIRness and the linked-data model (SVA, BfR), 17th February 2021 and

[RAKIP](#) and RADAR model repositories (BfR), 18th February 2021.

These three days were similarly structured with an introductory session followed by live-demos of the tools and interactive exercises. Each workshop day was accompanied by a dedicated e-learning-course, where participants had access to material and data to attend the interactive exercises, an updated agenda for each day, further reading materials and all links being shared throughout the sessions. After the workshop days these e-learning-courses also provided the slides and recordings of the sessions to repeat the contents afterwards.

The final day on Friday 19th February was introduced by a keynote about podcasting in One Health followed by a plenary discussion on “Digital innovation needs in One Health” with participants from BfR, SVA and EFSA. In the subsequent session “Digital innovation sharing forum” participants contributed to the programme by presenting their software or tool they are currently developing. Six different tools from participants were presented here. After the wrap up and close of the module the BfR-Organising Team provided individual support time for all participants to provide feedback, ask questions to the software developer teams in dedicated breakout sessions if needed and to bring up new feature requests or development goals.

Participants were able to reach out to the presenters via chat to ask questions, or if they wish also to use audio and video to ask questions in dedicated Q&A sessions. An overview of the event programme is provided in Annex 3.

E-Learning Structure

Accompanying e-learning courses on <https://bfr-elearning.de/> were provided by beginning of February 2021 and are still open to be accessed by all participants at least until end of November 2021. Eleven dedicated courses were created focusing on different software tools. They can be taken on the participants own pace to test and improve their knowledge and can be conducted independently from the presence courses.

Eight dedicated courses were set up to provide event related pre-reading materials on e.g. organisational issues, workshop material, Zoom links for the online event and questionnaires about permissions for pictures and recordings for the preparation and review of the thematic workshops days.

Each of the above mentioned courses offered a forum to ask questions. Contact details of the developers and the tutors were also available.

▼ E-Learning RAKIP

- 🗑 Introduction into the RAKIP Framework
- 🗑 Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) Format
- 🗑 The RAKIP Model Repository
- 🗑 The RADAR Model Repository
- 🗑 The RAKIP_portal Virtual Research Environment
- 🗑 The Food Modelling Journal (FMJ)
- 🗑 Introduction into KNIME
- 🗑 The Food Safety Knowledge (FSK-Lab) Software
- 🗑 The MIRARAM Model Annotation Guidelines
- 🗑 Feedback on RAKIP courses

▼ Platform-QuickStart

- 🗑 Introduction to the BfR E-Learning Platform

▼ CPD-Workshop

- 🗑 Info For Speakers
- 🗑 Event Introduction
- 🗑 Day 1 Joint Presentation Session 15th February
- 🗑 Day 2 Interactive Workshops I 16th February
- 🗑 Day 3 Interactive Workshops II 17th February
- 🗑 Day 4 Interactive Workshops III 18th February
- 🗑 Day 5 Plenary discussion and Q&A 19th February

Figure 2 Event and workshop-related courses

▼ E-Learning FoodChain-Lab

- 🗑 FoodChain-Lab Desktop Application

▼ E-Learning LinkedData

- 🗑 Linked Open Data (LOD)

Figure 1 Tool and software-related courses

Logistical arrangements

A housekeeping introduction slide with the expected structure of each day and information on pictures and recordings provided clarity.

For the opening of the event, coffee and lunch breaks, a slide with consistent imagery from the flyers was used.

A Zoom background for all the speakers in the event helped to clearly identify presenters and improve professional appearance. This also gave the impression, that despite these speakers being from different institutes, they were all working towards the same goal and are one team.

Participants were able to reach out to the presenters via chat to ask questions, or if they wish also to use audio and video to ask questions in dedicated Q&A sessions and discussions which were not recorded. The presenters also referred to the forum sections of each e-learning course to ask questions or referred to the dedicated email account of the event. Contact details of the developers and tutors were also available in the e-learning platform.

To enter the e-learning platform, every participant had to accept a privacy notice which gave everyone transparent information on the kind of data which were used and collected in the platform and contact details to the BfR privacy officer.

The local organisers used Zoom meetings to host the event. Participants received a link and login credentials together with joining instructions within the e-learning platform. On the first day of the event the organisers also sent out a message through the Moodle system (aiming the participants email addresses) where the link could be accessed as well.

In addition, delegates as well as participants were offered four dedicated Zoom test sessions in the week prior to the event to test the platform, test screen sharing and Zoom backgrounds. Some internal test sessions with the local organising team were set up on plus to test features like breakout sessions.

The BfR-Organising Team also received training on e-learning-course creation by the Moodle service provider. The BfR-Team also offered internal knowledge exchange training sessions considering and discussing the special features of online training and its implementation as well a weekly fixed day beginning in January 2021 for the team involved.

Accreditation

This workshop from 15th to 19th February 2021 has received approved accreditation by the Akademie für tierärztliche Fortbildung (Academy for Veterinary Continuing Education, ATF), which is 22 ATF hours for this workshop. The ATF of the Bundestierärztekammer

(Federal Chamber of Veterinary Surgeons, BTK) is responsible for the certification of continuing education courses for veterinarians. The ATF hours are registered as Continuing Education (CE) credits in Germany, which can be converted into CE credits in other countries. For any further questions on how to convert the ATF hours participants should directly contact the appropriate authority of their country. A conversion example of conversion in Austria and Switzerland was provided by the ATF.^[1]

In order to obtain accreditation, an application form was submitted which was approved by the ATF after a review of several criteria like e.g. the content and qualification of speakers.

Promotional Campaign

The promotional campaign was managed by the One Health EJP Communications Team and began in November 2020, one week after the first CPD module event, with a 'Save the Date' promotional flyer. It communicated the theme of the workshop, dates, location and target audience. As this was a consortium-only event, this first flyer was disseminated through the internal OHEJP communication channels (monthly education and training activities bulletin) and on the OHEJP website and social media channels when applicable. This was also sent to the Med-Vet-Net Association.

A dedicated web-page was also created in November 2020. The full flyer aimed to provide more detailed information about the concept and theme of the workshop, the aims and objectives and target audience. It also provided a link to the application form created by the BfR-Team on LimeSurvey, which was provided on a BfR-internal server, along with the deadline. This was also disseminated on a full flyer with the programme by mid December 2020 before Christmas holidays, through the same internal channels described for the save the date flyer. Confirmed speakers were asked to provide short biographies and a photo. These were added to the website page as they were received.

The accreditation of the course by the German ATF came right in time to be communicated in the One Health EJP Education and Training Bulletin in January 2021 which was sent out on 22nd January 2021. Registration deadline for the event was 25th January 2021.

The organisers opened a late registration for the new OHEJP consortium member institutes by email registration until Wednesday 10th February 2021. This was disseminated in the One Health EJP Education and Training Bulletin in February 2021 which was sent out on 5th of February 2021.

¹ Cf. <https://www.bundestieraerztekammer.de/d.php?id=6260>

The applications went through an internal selection procedure. Alongside with the acceptance of their application delegates also received their access data to the e-learning-platform with links to the first organisational courses they should pay attention to. There were a number of pre-requirements to complete e.g. a questionnaire to obtain permission of pictures and recordings needed to be filled in.

The communications team created branded visual montages from the screenshots and testimonials captured. These montages were used to report and share the successes of this workshop through a blog post on the One Health EJP website blog. This was signposted on the home page and CPD webpage. This was shared through the One Health EJP social media channels Twitter and LinkedIn, and the following monthly education and training activities bulletins published in 2021.

Applications and selection procedure

Based on the application form examples provided by the Comms team, the BfR-Team setup a registration form on LimeSurvey for participants. The application deadline closed by 25th January 2021. Considering new members (from Finland, Lithuania and Latvia) through late registration, the organisers received 66 eligible applications which were all accepted. The organisers accepted six applications from non-consortium members. A total of 55 participants attended.

Delegates

55 delegates finally attended the online event, from early-career researchers over PhD students, up to senior scientists, all from over 15 countries. Five delegates from stakeholders came from European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and European Medicines Agency (EMA). Six non-consortium members attended the workshop. The event benefited from their attendance as they actively contributed to the topics and provided excellent testimonials which are used for promotional purposes. Eleven accepted participants actually did not show up at the event. Below a graphic shows their educational background and affiliated country.

Figure 1 Delegates educational background

Figure 2 Delegates affiliated country

Course Evaluation

Evaluation forms were completed before the attendance activity. Each day of the module provided a different kind of feedback form with questions regarding the specific delivery mode of each day. The evaluation form of the last day collected the overall feedback and testimonials.

Certificates of Attendance

The BfR-Organising Team provided two kinds of certificates, created by the communications team: either with or without ATF hours. Participants were asked to complete a questionnaire to identify the type of certificate they would like to receive.

On the first day, the BfR-Organising Team explained that certificates were only being awarded for the whole week's attendance. This procedure of course kept the participants daily engagement high. After each day, participants actively confirmed that they fully participated the whole day by filling in an "attendance activity" in the e-learning courses of each workshop day. The attendance activity and the Zoom lists were compared afterwards. Based on these data, certificates were created and disseminated via email.

Blog Post

Work Package 6 worked closely with the One Health EJP Communications Team to create a blog post to promote the successes of the event, publish photos and testimonials. The published blog post can be found on the One Health EJP website [here](#).

This blog post was shared through the One Health EJP social media channels Twitter and LinkedIn, and the following monthly education and training activities bulletins published in 2021, with the first being in March 2021.

Testimonials

Permission to publish these testimonials was obtained during the event registration process. Any participants or lecturers who had not responded, were reminded to provide a response during the evaluation, or within 7 days after the event.

Examples of Delegate Testimonials collected

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FEBRUARY 2021

BfR
Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung

"A really great opportunity for young people. At the webinar, I felt like we all had one goal: to save public health, to save the world. That is the biggest thought and message I carry with me from this webinar."
Amil Orahovac
Centre of Excellence for Digitalisation of Microbial Food Safety Risk Assessment and Quality Parameters for Accurate Food Authenticity Certification, Montenegro

"A good way to look the state of the art of One Health tools."
Antonio Rodriguez Hernández
INIA, Spain

"The event exceeded my initial expectations. The hands-on exercises are reproducible for further practice on your own and I appreciated the speakers' availability to provide further support when exploring the tools, if needed."
Mariel Aybar Espinoza
BfR, Germany

"The One Health EJP CPD module was an engaging opportunity to learn about new tools and discuss their utility with creators directly."
Patrick Lennard
Leiden University Medical Centre, Netherlands

"Is was a pleasure to participate in One Health EJP CPD module. It helped to think from another angle in risk assessment."
Rimvydas Falkauskas
National Food and Veterinary Risk Assessment Institute, Lithuania

"I am grateful for having the opportunity to be with the highest scientists in the field! I didn't expect to receive such a high quantity of information and guidance in using the new technology. And all presented very simple and easy to do."
Adrian Ardelean, Veterinary Attaché
Permanent Representation of Romania to the EU

Photos

Permission to publish these photos was obtained during the event registration process. The face and names of any participants or lecturers who had not provided permission were blurred to adhere to the GDPR regulations.

**ne
HEALTH EJP**

**CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL
DEVELOPMENT MODULE
FEBRUARY 2021**

Thank you to all for making
the workshop such a success!

BfR
Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung
CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT MODULE 2021
Continuing Professional Development for One Health practitioners

FAIR
Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable

BfR RAKIP-Web
Live Demo and Exercises
Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung
Continuing Professional Development for One Health practitioners

FoodChain-Lab
An innovative tool to increase food safety through supply chain analysis
Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung

How to define your audience?

BfR
Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung

Internal Events Survey information

The European Commission (EC) requires all dissemination and communication activities, and events to be reported. This information has been reported through the Internal Events Survey on the OHEJP website, which collects data and is reported to the EC.

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP's Second CPD module		
Date:	15 th to 19 th February 2021		
Place:	Online Workshop (Zoom) with accompanying e-learning course		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	Yes
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	No
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	90	Media	0
Industry	2	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Annex 1: "Save the Date" Promotional Flyer

Save the Date!
One Health EJP
Continuing Professional Development Module
Digital innovations for One Health practitioners
Training on innovative digital software solutions supporting risk assessment, zoonotic outbreak investigations and data interoperability

Date and Location:

E-Learning Course (own pace, self organised): 1st – 26th February 2021

Online Workshop: 15th – 19th February 2021

Audience:

OHEJP consortium members with interest in One Health-related IT applications. PhD Students & Early Career Researchers highly welcome.

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ONE Health EJP

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Annex 2: Full Promotional Flyer

One Health EJP
Continuing Professional Development Module
Digital innovations for One Health practitioners
Training on innovative digital software solutions supporting risk assessment, zoonotic outbreak investigations and data interoperability

Date and Location:

E-Learning Course (own pace, self organised): 1st – 26th February 2021
Online Workshop: 15th – 19th February 2021

Audience:

OHEJP consortium members with interest in One Health-related IT applications. PhD Students & Early Career Researchers highly welcome.

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What is the aim of this CPD Module?

This module will be a one-week virtual training on innovative digital software solutions supporting risk assessment, zoonotic outbreak investigations and data interoperability. The presented software tools support researchers and One Health professionals in various data collection and analysis tasks including those linked with outbreak investigations and the trace back of food products. The presented solutions have the potential to support the whole One Health community including national and international risk assessment agencies, risk managers and academic institutions.

Dedicated full day workshops will be hosted by senior research scientists from the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) and the Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) that have a long track record in providing trainings to research scientists from different research domains (specifically food science, but also for researchers in public health and animal health).

The CPD Module encompasses:

- **Day 1:** In a joint **presentation session** invited experts, e.g. from several EJP projects and European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), will provide examples for the various needs and selected digital innovation solutions which can be applied to scenarios from the domains of food safety, public health and animal health.
- **Day 2 to 4:** In the three following days **interactive thematic workshops** with practical exercises on specific software tools will be conducted:
 - [FoodChain-Lab](#) (BfR, EFSA);
 - [Data interoperability in One Health: data FAIRness and the linked-data model](#) (SVA, BfR);
 - Knowledge exchange via [online model repositories](#) (BfR).

These workshops will demonstrate specific application scenarios of the different software solutions and include hands-on exercises for the participants.
- **Day 5:** In a **plenary discussion** with different experts there will be the opportunity to discuss questions from the participants.
- An accompanying **E-learning course** provides workshop material for the preparation and review of the thematic workshops and can be used by the participants to test and improve their knowledge.

To register for this event click [here](#).

Registration closes at 12 midnight CET on 25th January 2021.

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Annex 3: Event Programme

One Health EJP CPD Module 2021 Digital innovations for One Health practitioners

Training on innovative digital software solutions supporting risk assessment, zoonotic outbreak investigations and data interoperability

Day 1 - 15th February Joint Presentation Session

10.00-10.15 CET	<p>Welcome and opening Karsten Nöckler, German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)</p>
10.15-10.30	<p>CPD course introduction and housekeeping Matthias Filter, BfR</p>
10.30-11.30	<p>Links between quantitative risk assessments and expert judgements – the future of scientific policy advice Olaf Mosbach-Schulz, European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)</p>
11.30-12.00	<p>Risk-benefit assessment of foods – how an emerging research domain could benefit from timely digital innovation initiatives Maarten Nauta, National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark (DTU Food)</p>
12.00-13.00	<p>Lunch break</p>
13.00-13.30	<p>Open science publishing and “living articles” Lyubomir Penev, Teodor Georgiev, Pensoft Publishers</p>
13.30-14.00	<p>rStrainSelect: an R-tool for sampling strains based on metadata in a One Health context Laurent Guillier, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES)</p>
14.00-15.00	<p>Dashboards as strategy to integrate multiple data streams for real time surveillance Alexander Ullrich, Robert Koch Institute (RKI)</p>
15.00-15.30	<p>Fast meets slow: building sustainable digital systems for bioinformatics based surveillance Karin Lagesen, Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI)</p>
15.30-16.00	<p>Introductions to the upcoming workshop days Marion Gottschald, Matthias Filter, BfR and Fernanda Dórea, Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA)</p>

Day 2 - 16th February Interactive Workshops I

10.00-10.30	<p>FoodChain-Lab: an innovative tool to increase food safety through supply chain analyses Marion Gottschald, Alexander Falenski, Marco Rügen, BfR</p>
10.30-11.15	<p>Analytical features of FoodChain-Lab and successful applications in outbreak analyses (live demo) Marion Gottschald, Alexander Falenski, Marco Rügen, BfR</p>
11.15-12.00	<p>Getting started with the FoodChain-Lab web application Marion Gottschald, Alexander Falenski, Marco Rügen, BfR</p>
12.00-13.00	<p>Lunch break</p>
13.00-15.30	<p>Interactive traceability exercise using the FoodChain-Lab web application Marion Gottschald, Alexander Falenski, Marco Rügen, BfR</p>

Day 3 - 17th February Interactive Workshops II

10.00-12.00	<p>Data interoperability in One Health: data FAIRness and the linked-data model – Introduction Fernanda Dórea, SVA</p>
12.00-13.00	<p>Lunch break</p>
13.00-15.00	<p>Data interoperability in One Health: data FAIRness and the linked-data model – Exercises Fernanda Dórea, SVA, Taras Günther, Estibaliz Lopez de Abechucio Garrido, Nazareno Scaccia, BfR</p>

One Health EJP CPD Module 2021

Digital innovations for One Health practitioners

Training on innovative digital software solutions supporting risk assessment, zoonotic outbreak investigations and data interoperability

Day 4 - 18th February Interactive Workshops III

10.00-10.30 CET	Online model repositories – Introduction Matthias Filter, Petra Ganas, Thomas Schüler, Lars Valentin, BfR
10.30-11.30	RAKIP introduction and live demo Matthias Filter, Petra Ganas, Thomas Schüler, Lars Valentin, BfR
11.30-12.30	<i>Lunch break</i>
12.30-13.30	RAKIP exercises for participants Matthias Filter, Thomas Schüler, Petra Ganas, Lars Valentin, BfR
13.30-16.00	RADAR repository introduction, live demo and exercises (tbc) Jakub Fusiak, BfR

Day 5 - 19th February Plenary discussion and Q&A

09.30-09.45	Keynote: Podcasting in One Health Sara Perestrelo, BfR
09.45-11.30	Plenary discussion – digital innovation needs in One Health Panel tba
11.00-12.00	Participant's digital innovation sharing forum
12.00-13.00	<i>Lunch break</i>
13.00-14.45	Q&A, feedback and support BfR
14.45-15.00	Plenary wrap-up and close of the module BfR